
A STATUS REPORT OF THE NATIONAL DIGITAL LIBRARY OF INDIA

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DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.7183886

Abstract:

Wide geographic region and large diverse population of India is the main barrier to spreading education to the masses. Today now in the 'Digital India Era' digital libraries become a boon for the education system. The government uses technology in many of its activities, and providing high-quality education is among them. A one-stop source for all information needs is the National Digital Library of India (NDLI), it gives access to wide range of information by sources, file types, subjects, and educational levels to anyone and anywhere 24*7. The present paper aims to analyze the current status of NDLI. The information gathered for the latest work from the NDLI's official website and then further evaluated to meet the project goal.

Keywords: NDLI, digital library, Data analysis, Library Services, Collection

Introduction:

The exponential growth of information has made it more impossible to retrieve particular information for users and purchase all documents for the library because funds are limited. The effect has been that users have become more dependent upon external sources other than parent institutions. For that digital libraries have emerged as a solution for the information need. Digital libraries have their advantages as compared to traditional libraries. Digital library resources and services are available everywhere and anywhere. To support this open access movement, to cater to countless users, and to meet the new philosophy of Digital

India. The MHRD, now the Ministry of Education launched the National Digital Library of India project. NDL has been providing a home page in 11 languages English, Japanese, Kannada, Chinese, Assamese, Bengali, Hindi, Navajo, Oriya, Sanskrit, and Spanish.

Students from kindergarten to graduate level scholars can benefit greatly from the NDLI. NDLI was created by IIT Kharagpur and released in 2016 by the MHRD, or Ministry of Human Resource Development, currently known as the Government of India's Ministry of Education, as part of its National Mission on Education through Information and Communication Technology

(NMEICT).NDLI's goal is to provide information and communication technology-based education on a unified platform. In order to help users, discover the correct information quickly, the NDLI offers filtered and federated searches. NDLI provide information to people in all fields, from the school level to postdocs.It behaves like a single window device. As a one-stop-shop for all digital educational resources, NDLI offers a single-pane search capability. In other words, it is a “custom service” that is provided in an integrated environment 24 hours a day, 365 days a year, according to user needs.

Objectives:

- 1) To evaluate the collection at the National Digital Library of India.
- 2) To find out the different types of Resource.
- 3) To find out the different types of Subjects.
- 4) To find out the different types of sources.
- 5) To find out the different types of Learning Resources.

Review of the Literature:

Lots of studies were done on NDLI with different perceptions of authors. Katre Dinesh(2004) also stated that the learner-centric approach should be opted for while developing digital libraries in India and, systematic efforts would be done to aware users about digital libraries. Chauhan Suresh and Mahajan Priti (2013) discussed how UGC took initiative to develop digital content via a digital consortium to strengthen library collection. Bhoi Nabakumar and Bhue Shiba(2015)also stated that NDLI is become a new philosophy of digital India and will serve as a milestone in this journey. Darandale and Adinath(2017) did

a detailed swot analysis of NDLI. He found a lot of strength in NDLI but needs to concentrate on weaknesses and threats too. Mangurkar Medha(2018) did content analysis of NDLI. Bisma Bashir, Fayoz Loan, and Nahida Nasreen(2019) provide a detailed overview of NDLI followed by problems arising with NDLI as e-resources.

Methodology:

The National Digital Library of India website collected data as of 25 September 2022. (<https://ndl.iitkgp.ac.in/>)

Data Analysis:

Search by Resource:

According to research articles, the majority of digital libraries contain e-books, electronic journals, electronic magazines, and other standard digital materials. Although NDLI now encompasses a wide range of digital content, including apps, simulations, animations, databases, and other types of digital content not hitherto included in a single digital library, it also includes digital content for conventional commodities.

Table 1: Types of Resources

Sr. No.	Type of Resource	Items
1	Text	84,344,697
2	Image	1,621,698
3	Video	635,202
4	Audio	260,252
5	Presentations	178,107
6	Simulations	11,518
7	Applications	2,509
8	Animation	911

(Source: <https://ndl.iitkgp.ac.in/>)

Figure 1: Graphical analysis of the type of Resources

Search by Subject:

Table 2: Types of Subject Category

Sr. No	Subject Category	Items
1	Computer Science, Information & general works	16,623,996
2	Philosophy & Psychology	630,386
3	Religion	249,334
4	Social Science	6,342,226
5	Languages	206,289
6	Natural Science and Mathematics	9,919,051
7	Technology	12,850,725
8	The arts, fine & decorative arts	1,974,273
9	Literature & rhetoric	995,432
10	History & geography	1,227,536

(Source: <https://ndl.iitkgp.ac.in/>)

Figure 2: Graphical analysis of types of Subjects

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Search by Source:

Table 3: Types of Source

Sr. No.	Source	Items
1	British Council	656,861
2	Joint Admission Board of IITs	37
3	Graduate Aptitude Test in Engineering	183
4	NPTEL	151,279
5	NCERT	6,235
6	South Asia Archive	29,969
7	OECD iLibrary	102,017
8	Librivox	206,672
9	KrishiKosh-Indian National Agricultural Research System	138,322
10	Inflibnet-Shodhganga	269,702
11	Inflibnet-Shodhganga	1,930
12	Inflibnet-N-LIST-Oxford Scholarship Online	771
13	Satyajit Ray Society	39
14	World eBook Library	7,526,585

(Source: <https://ndl.iitkgp.ac.in/>)

Figure 3: Graphical analysis of types of Sources

Search by Learning Resource:

NDL India provides access to the following types of content from various sources: Books, articles, dissertations, manuscripts, webcourses, etc.

Table 4: Types of Learning Resource

S. No	Learning Resources	Items	S. No	Learning Resources	Items
1.	Audiobook	233,966	22.	Broadcast	27,520
2.	Book Review	76,555	23.	Brochure	2,281
3.	Booklet	5,327	24.	Calendar	4,626
4.	Case study	186,542	25.	Catalog	58,346
5.	Newspaper	14,690,640	26.	Chapter	330,678
6.	Periodical	15048	27.	Chart	430
7.	Photograph	1,368,324	28.	Collection	13,865
8.	Poster	10,062	29.	Conference Proceeding	155,916
9.	Script	88,285	30.	Correspondence	141,530
10.	Activity	46,629	31.	Data Set	242,141
11.	Agreement	150	32.	Diagram	213
12.	Album	96	33.	Diary	180
13.	Almanac	3,552	34.	Directory	1,957
14.	Annual Report	34,357	35.	Discussion	31,481
15.	Appendix	1,349	36.	Doubt Clearing	326
16.	Article	42,661,211	37.	Educational App	1,899
17.	Audio Lecture	3,777	38.	Educational Game	5,279
18.	Autobiography	6,125	39.	eMail	165
19.	Bibliography	6,125	40.	Exercise	38,021
20.	Biography	11,642	41.	Film	4,811
21.	Book	7,547,190	42.	Gazetteer	2,682
43.	Graph	318	78.	Podcast Presentation	1,476
44.	Handout	389	79.	Poetry	21,791
45.	Hands-on	8,381	80.	Preprint	21,713
46.	Historical Record	533,719	81.	Presentation	206,632
47.	Indicator	490	82.	Proceeding	135,906
48.	Interview	454	83.	Project Report	6,547
49.	Issue	18,763	84.	Question	16,522
50.	Journal	248,887	85.	Question Paper	38,885
51.	Journal Review	1	86.	Question Paper Part	240
52.	Key Table	541	87.	Question Set	38,002
53.	Lab Material	13,244	88.	Quiz	2,407
54.	Law Act	875,164	89.	Recognition	78
55.	Law Judgement	878,483	90.	Report	678,031
56.	Law Report	6,351	91.	Research Highlight	2,708
57.	Law Scribe	620	92.	Review	53,197
58.	Leaflet	3,215	93.	Self-Assessment	6,994
59.	Lecture Notes	23,328	94.	Series	6,857
60.	Lesson Plan	9,586	95.	Simulation	7,875
61.	Letter	183,730	96.	Source Code	105,05
62.	Magazine	23,509	97.	Specimen	1,551
63.	Manuscript	171,306	98.	Standard	12,313
64.	Map	58,787	99.	Story	19,286
65.	Media Article	6	100.	Summary	8,362
66.	Media Act	2	101.	Survey	3,328
67.	Model Answer	505	102.	Syllabus	2,232
68.	Monograph	19,223	103.	Synopsis	26,692
69.	Music	4,984	104.	Teacher's Manual	1,126
70.	Music Notation	65,286	105.	Technical Manual	2,656
71.	Newspaper Article	7,443,377	106.	Technical Report	716,629
72.	News Letter	13,720	107.	Thesis	760,880
73.	Notes	70,665	108.	Training Manual	941
74.	Painting	6,334	109.	Transcript	1,901
75.	Patent	166,008	110.	Video Lecture	457,819
76.	Plan	11,574	111.	Visual Artwork	2,893
77.	Play	3,365	112.	Web Course	17,318

(Source: <https://ndl.iitkgp.ac.in/>)

Scope and Limitations:

This paper's goal is to review the current services and facilities of NDLI. The current status of resources is limited to NDLI.

Conclusion:

One of the most comprehensive online information sources right now is the NDLI. NDLI offers useful answers by giving metadata of information resources, even though the information explosion will cause consumers to become confused about where to search for information. The updated NDLI has incorporated new elements like the COVID-19 research repository, the Disability Knowledge NDLI club, and test preparation. Despite these challenges, raising awareness of the NDLI, educating its users, and promoting the use of the National Digital Library show that the NDLI is a vast information resource.

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